

Study of Myanmar Language Research and Its Impact

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There have been numerous studies and research works related to natural language processing (NLP) part of language research, highlighting the work in context with Myanmar language [1-7]. Syntactic analysis of the language was done in [1] where the researchers attempted analysis of Myanmar language in terms of all the syntaxes. A researcher from India [2] studied annotated bibliography for Burmese language of Myanmar. Tun et al. (2008) studied segmentation of the language and made analysis of the language in terms of words of the sentences [3]. Pann et al. (2011) worked on search engine for Myanmar language [4]. Parsing analysis of Myanmar language was done using function tagging in [5]. Yuzana et al. (2008) presented a study that is based on analogy for sounds like name matching and learning the language [6]. Win et al. (2017) suggested some framework for language study related to Facebook comments in Myanmar language [7]. All these research works analyze the language and attempt to develop some dictionary, bibliography and syntaxes for better and efficient use of the language.

There have been enormous studies on NLP part of the Myanmar language but this paper mainly attempts to bring out the research work purely in the field of Myanmar language.

2. RELATED RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

We investigated the quantum of studies and research in the field of Myanmar language, though few could be seen in

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a study about how much research has been carried out in the field of Myanmar language by the researchers, scholars and academicians in Myanmar and outside Myanmar. Language is a very important factor in national unity and strength and therefore this study brings an impact analysis of the amount of research work in this much demanding topic. The research studies both on natural language processing (NLP) and core language usage are critically analyzed and few important recommendations are suggested that could further help the young researchers to carry out the research in this direction.

KEYWORDS: Myanmar language, research, study, impact

1. INTRODUCTION

Myanmar language is spoken by most of the people all across the country. This language has got wide usage and popularity among all the people and also many Chinese and Indian origin persons living there. While interacting with foreigners visiting Myanmar, the language is reported and called as very sweet-spoken language. Foreigners like few greetings very much like, Minga lar par (Greeting), Kyae zu tin par tal (Thanks) etc. Research is something that studies about all happenings and activities in the areas of science, engineering, technology, mathematics, social sciences, humanities, languages; and therefore it becomes pertinent to also have knowledge of the amount of research work which has been done by different groups of people that may include scholars, students, social scientists, researchers, faculty members or any one.

literature but mostly highlighting grammar and NLP part of Myanmar language analysis; and very few on core language research. Few of them is studied here what how exactly various researchers have done the work.

Asia Foundation Report (2016) suggests wonderful facts about role of mother tongue in effective teaching learning process. It has given few important case studies why and how Myanmar language based delivery system in teaching learning could of great help. This study and report suggests that the use of Myanmar language vis-à-vis other languages need to be properly researched upon and studied so that further action plan can be taken up [8]. Gender in-equality, skill development and mass awareness are all affected by the mother tongue so the effectiveness of its use and outreach needs to be investigated.

British Academy organized a workshop on the different languages used in Asia, especially Malaysia, Thailand and Myanmar in higher education [9]. The summary of report suggests that different languages and their impact in learning outcome of higher education system is different.

Wai Mon et al. (2011) studied English as Foreign Language (EFL) among Myanmar people and assesses various attitudes using EFL in different activities. Learning aptitude, motivation for learning, study based approaches etc., were focus of study with regard to EFL among Myanmar [10]. This

suggests that the attitudes in learning process has some influence of EFL and so of Burmese as well. Myanmar language has to be comparatively studied with other languages in terms of not only aptitude but attitude also.

Ward Keeler (2007) in his editorial on Bulletin for Burmese studies, brought out several findings on instruction materials, challenges and opportunities in using the instruction materials. Linguistics were studied from point of view of both teachers and learners. Though the findings are extensive but impact of Myanmar language research for which we are interested could not be seen [11]. Journal of Burma Studies [12] highlights about culture and increasing role of women and there also Myanmar language research can be of some importance.

James (2011) in his PhD thesis investigated and studied in detail about articulatory and acoustic sound in Burmese tone. Pitch, intensity, vowel sounds, quality of syllables etc. were factors in his study. This work is very important that directly deals with Myanmar language usage and how does it impress upon the recipients based on various attributes of acoustics and sounds of words and letters. Burmese phonology and phonetics were studied and investigated with the help of suitable experimentation, we are not stressing upon technical part the work but trying to highlight the impact of the work in the area of Myanmar language research [13].

Thein Lwin (2011) in his article [14] writes about role of languages in context with Myanmar. Linguistic diversity is discussed safeguarding the identity of Myanmar language. The use of language in different parts of Myanmar in slightly different manner in Shan State, Sagaing region and others is studied. Teaching of minority languages is studied also. This article looks most suitable that we can say that the author has attempted a contribution in the field of Myanmar language exclusively. Various issues related to policies, stakeholders and policymakers are also discussed.

Based on key contributions that were studied critically what we can find as statements for problem towards research activities in the area of Myanmar language:

- Research work in specific field of use of language us very limited
- Since the research is limited, not even a single research paper could be seen studying what is the impact of Myanmar language and its research
- The studies and research contributions are mostly on NLP that is using some soft computing methods for analysis of language. This is a computer based analysis with the help of suitable algorithm of NLP.
- The research on languages, variations, impact on learning attitude, skill development, training, awareness is limited, rather do not exit
- The number of PhDs and other dissertation works is not available online. Only few titles can be seen but the details of the work could not be accessed.

3. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on study of few important contributions both in the field of NLP part of Myanmar language and core research on Myanmar language, following is the recommendation:

- Focused research is necessary for making language research in Myanmar as an asset.

- More seminars and workshops are required to bring out selected number of people who are working in Myanmar language.
- Lot of work related to Myanmar sign language is needed since there has been very limited research on Myanmar sign language
- The study on how the language research can promote strong culture, strength and unity especially among rural people.
- Societal impact of language research is required to be made.
- Need to study about how does mother tongue affect teaching learning and skill development.
- The language affects attitude for learning and thus this is also necessary for further study regarding how Myanmar language influences various attitudes and motivation in students in terms of learning outcome.

Few steps could be easily understood with the help of a diagram, shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Steps of Myanmar language research and study of its impact.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper brings out an important issue which can have significant impact towards action plan for research activities in Myanmar language. We have studied a number available research works and studies on Myanmar language and attempted to find the impact created by the existing work. The paper also recommends major suggestions for enriching the research in core area of Myanmar language, based on the gap analysis made. The future work of this work aims at focusing on certain specific domain of study in Myanmar language.

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